

A SURVEY AMONG BULGARIAN STUDENTS ON MEDICAL METAPHORICAL TERMS FROM THE FIELDS OF ORTHOPAEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY

Zheleva Z.

Medical University of Plovdiv, Department of Languages and Specialised Training, Senior Lecturer

Abstract

The present paper investigates the role and function of metaphor in medical terminology, with a specific focus on Orthopaedics and Traumatology. Metaphorical language facilitates comprehension and retention among learners, bridging the gap between specialised knowledge and everyday understanding. Drawing on established theories of metaphor, the study examines how such expressions influence medical students' conceptual grasp and their accuracy in using them. A survey conducted among Bulgarian medical students at the Medical University of Plovdiv assessed their recognition and understanding of metaphorical terminology from the Orthopaedics and Traumatology syllabus. Overall, the study highlights the dual nature of metaphor—as a cognitive aid that enhances learning and memory, and as a potential source of misunderstanding when applied imprecisely.

Keywords: medical conditions, metaphor, medical terminology, orthopaedics, traumatology, Bulgarian, students.

Language for specific purposes (LSP), such as the language of medicine, is viewed by scholars as a distinct linguistic subsystem possessing the structural and semantic features of general language while exhibiting specialized conventions and terminological rules (Cabre, 1999, p. 61). Medical language, while derived from the common linguistic framework, differs significantly in its semantic density, precision, and systematic categorization (Faber, 2012). Its specialized lexicon often seems difficult to comprehend by the general public. Nevertheless, certain linguistic mechanisms—particularly metaphor and metonymy—function as bridges between technical and common knowledge, helping both students and patients decode the vocabulary of medicine.

Latin and Greek are known to be the foundational languages of medical terminology—Greek as the language of early physicians like Hippocrates and Galen, and Latin as the *lingua franca* in Europe for centuries. Prefixes, roots, suffixes originating from the two languages enable physicians to construct complex medical diagnoses, diseases, signs and symptoms thus revealing the role of Latin and Greek in maintaining precision and universality in contemporary medical terminology. (Mirchev, Oprova: 2018)

By associating new and complex medical phenomena with familiar images, metaphors facilitate understanding and retention. In this sense, figurative language in medicine is not ornamental but functional, providing conceptual scaffolding for learners and professionals alike. Although traditionally associated with literature and poetry, metaphor and metonymy play a vital role in the conceptual architecture of scientific fields. As Kuhn (1993) observes, these figures of speech are integral to the way scientific disciplines reproduce and expand their theoretical frameworks, revealing their embeddedness in human cognition. Far from being peripheral, metaphor is thus a fundamental cognitive mechanism that contributes to scientific creativity and the construction of disciplinary knowledge.

The **classical view of metaphor**, dating back to Aristotle, perceives metaphor as a rhetorical device—essentially a stylistic substitution based on resemblance. Aristotle defines it as “giving a thing a name

that belongs to something else” (*Poetics*, 1457b), implying a simple transfer of meaning from one entity to another. In this framework, metaphor is primarily decorative, disconnected from cognitive processes and serving an aesthetic rather than conceptual purpose.

Later, the **comparison theory of metaphor** built upon this Aristotelian foundation by emphasizing that metaphor is an abbreviated simile, a linguistic form that highlights similarity between two entities (Ortony, 1979). According to this model, metaphor compresses or condenses comparison for rhetorical efficiency.

A significant departure from these earlier conceptions is **Max Black's interaction theory** (1954), which posits that metaphor operates through an interaction between a primary subject (the topic) and a secondary subject (the vehicle). Meaning arises not through substitution or resemblance alone, but through the dynamic interplay between these two domains, producing novel insights. In this framework, metaphor is inherently creative and generative, expanding semantic boundaries and enriching conceptual understanding.

The **Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT)** developed by Lakoff and Johnson marked a paradigm shift by asserting that metaphor is not merely a linguistic ornament but a fundamental mechanism of thought. According to this perspective, metaphors structure how humans perceive, conceptualize, and communicate experience. Abstract concepts, such as illness, health, or pain, are understood through mappings from specific, embodied experiences. Thus, metaphor constitutes the very foundation of cognition and is present across all domains of knowledge and everyday life (Lakoff & Johnson, 2004). Through conceptual mapping, metaphors enable individuals to make sense of abstract or complex phenomena by projecting the structure of familiar domains onto unfamiliar ones.

Building on this, **Fauconnier and Turner's Blending Theory** (also known as **Conceptual Integration Theory**) extends CMT by proposing that metaphor involves the integration of multiple mental spaces rather than a simple mapping between two. These mental spaces interact and blend dynamically, giving rise to emergent meanings not contained in any single input. The theory thus emphasizes the creative synthesis of

concepts during linguistic and cognitive processing (Fauconnier & Turner, 2002).

Finally, **Relevance Theory** (Sperber & Wilson) approaches metaphor from a pragmatic standpoint, suggesting that interpretation is guided by context and the listener's inferential processes. Here, metaphorical meaning is derived through optimal relevance, balancing cognitive effort with interpretative reward. The listener reconstructs the speaker's intended meaning beyond literal expression, making metaphor an act of cognitive negotiation rather than mere substitution.

Applying these theoretical frameworks to medical language reveals how physicians, students, and even patients conceptualize the human body and disease through metaphorical models. Medical discourse frequently employs **blended metaphors** that combine elements from physical, mechanical, or military domains. For example, the **immune system** is conceptualized as a defence force that "attacks" pathogens, **cells** are described as "soldiers," and **disease** as an "invader." The **heart** is commonly referred to as a "pump," the **kidneys** as "filters," and **cancer treatment** as a "battle." The sources of medical metaphors are remarkably diverse. They draw upon **colors** (e.g., *blue ear*), **human characteristics** (*wisdom tooth*), **animals** (*leopard skin*), **foods** (*pancake cells*), **plants** (*oak-leaf spots*), and **clothing** (*kneecap*). Some are **eponymous**, referencing mythological or historical figures (*Medusa head*). Such mappings help render abstract biological processes more tangible and relatable.

However, this reliance on metaphor introduces challenges in teaching and memorising medical terminology. While it simplifies and clarifies, it can also oversimplify, potentially distorting scientific accuracy or reinforcing misleading assumptions. Moreover, metaphors may carry cultural variations, leading to differences in interpretation across linguistic or cultural boundaries. Hence, while metaphor facilitates understanding, its use must be approached critically.

Metaphor permeates every branch of medicine, from anatomy to pathology, diagnosis, and therapy. Each speciality develops its own network of metaphorical images and concepts that render abstract ideas accessible. As Masukume (2012) notes, medical metaphors serve both didactic and communicative purposes, assisting learners in retaining information and professionals in conveying complex ideas succinctly.

This paper focuses specifically on metaphorical terminology within Orthopaedics and Traumatology, a field that abounds in vivid and visually descriptive expressions. These metaphors often describe deformities, symptoms, and treatment methods through analogies with animals, objects, or mythological figures. Terms such as *dancing patella*, *butterfly fracture*, *parrot's beak deformity*, *pigeon breast*, and *saber (yatagan) tibia* exemplify this pattern. Each expression combines a familiar, often specific image with a technical medical term, enabling students to visualize and remember the underlying pathology more effectively.

Although these expressions might sound colloquial or even peculiar, their use is deliberate and pedagogically motivated. They translate abstract anatomical and pathological concepts into specific visual imagery,

enhancing both understanding and memorization. In this way, metaphor serves as a bridge between the clinical and the cognitive, between the scientific precision of Latin or Greek terminology and the learner's need for tangible association. The medical terminology and especially the Latin and Greek terms and term elements present a challenge to medical students throughout the world (Mirchev, D., Oprova, Ya. (2024). And the mistakes in using it are not few, even diagnoses in the health legislation are mistakenly used in countries like Bulgaria where Latin is the language of medicine (Mirchev, D., Oprova, Ya. (2023).

To explore the educational value and recognition of metaphorical terminology in orthopaedics and traumatology, a questionnaire-based survey was designed. Ten metaphorical terms were selected from the course textbook in Orthopaedics and Traumatology used at the Medical University of Plovdiv. The course forms part of the curriculum for fourth- and fifth-year medical students, and the target participants were Bulgarian students.

A total of 52 respondents participated in the study. Each item in the questionnaire presented three possible answers, only one of which was fully correct, while the other two were partially correct or intentionally misleading to test the precision of understanding. The analysis of responses revealed distinct patterns of recognition. Terms that evoke strong visual metaphors (e.g., *butterfly fracture*, *pigeon breast*) or describe commonly encountered conditions achieved higher accuracy rates. In contrast, terms with less vivid imagery or linked to rare clinical phenomena showed lower recognition rates.

These outcomes confirm that the metaphoric vividness of a term directly correlates with its cognitive accessibility and ease of recall. Visual metaphors engage perceptual and associative memory, enabling learners to construct mental images of anatomical or pathological forms. However, the study also revealed that some students misinterpreted metaphorical terms literally, highlighting the risk of semantic ambiguity inherent in figurative language.

The findings of this study underscore the complex yet indispensable role of metaphor in medical education and communication. On one hand, metaphors provide a powerful cognitive framework for understanding abstract or invisible phenomena by anchoring them in sensory and experiential domains. On the other, their overuse or misapplication can obscure scientific precision or reinforce misconceptions.

In orthopaedics and traumatology, where visual diagnosis and spatial reasoning are essential, metaphorical language appears particularly effective. The imagery associated with deformities, fractures, and postural abnormalities creates mnemonic associations that enhance recall and diagnostic accuracy. However, this same imagery can become problematic when metaphors are translated across languages or cultures, potentially altering their interpretive resonance.

From a pedagogical perspective, the study suggests that explicit discussion of metaphorical language should be integrated into medical curricula. Teaching students to critically analyse the figurative dimensions

of medical terminology can promote both linguistic competence and conceptual clarity. Furthermore, awareness of metaphor's cognitive foundations—its

capacity to simplify, visualize, and systematize knowledge—can make medical education more accessible and reflective.

Question	Answer A	Answer B	Answer C	Correct answer	% of correct answers
Q1- танц на капачката (dancing patella)	22 (43%)	25 (49%)	4(8%)	B	49%
Q2- патешка походка (duck-like gait)	0(0%)	24 (47%)	27 (53%)	C	53%
Q3- гипсова превръзка тип Минерва (Minerva cast)	22 (43%)	15(29%)	14 (27%)	B	29%
Q4- мраморна болест (marble bone disease)	34(65%)	13(25%)	4 (8%)	A	65%
Q5- тибия ятаган (tibia yatagan)	34 (65%)	12(23%)	5 (10%)	A	65%
Q6- Жабешка поза (froggy position)	16(33%)	18 (35%)	17 (33%)	B	35%
Q7- Форма тип човка на папагал (parrot's beak form)	15 (29%)	30(59%)	6 (12%)	B	59%
Q8 – Пеперудообразна фрактура (butterfly-like fracture)	10(20%)	5 (10%)	36(70%)	C	70%
Q9- Деформация тип „птичи/кокоши гърди“ (pigeon breast deformity)	7 (14%)	1 (2%)	43 (84%)	C	84%
Q10- Конско ходило (clubfoot deformity)	44 (88%)	3 (6%)	3 (6%)	A	88%

Analysis of the questionnaire revealed marked variability in students' recognition accuracy, with correct response rates ranging from 29% to 88%. This distribution indicates substantial differences in familiarity with specific orthopaedic and traumatological terms. The data suggest that both the visual-metaphoric nature of certain terms and their clinical frequency of use significantly influence recognition performance.

High performance ($\geq 70\%$ correct)

The highest rates of correct responses were recorded for **Q8 (butterfly-shaped fracture, 70%)**, **Q9 (pigeon/chicken breast deformity, 84%)**, and **Q10 (equinus or "horse's" foot, 88%)**. These entities share a strong *metaphoric and visual correspondence* between the medical term and the physical appearance of the condition. For instance, the *butterfly* configuration of a fracture fragment or the *pigeon chest* deformity evoke vivid and concrete imagery, facilitating memory retention and recognition. The clarity and universality of these metaphors likely contribute to their high correct response rates. Such results suggest that terms with direct visual analogies are more intuitively understood and recalled, even in the absence of extensive clinical experience.

Average performance (40–69% correct)

Moderate performance was observed for **Q1 (dancing patella, 49%)**, **Q2 (duck-like gait, 53%)**, **Q4 (marble bone disease, 65%)**, **Q5 (tibia yatagan, 65%)**, and **Q7 (parrot-beak deformity, 59%)**. These terms are also metaphorically derived, yet their imagery

is often less immediately anatomical or less commonly encountered in everyday practice. For example, while *marble bone disease* (osteopetrosis) conveys density and hardness, the metaphor is abstract rather than visual. Similarly, *duck-like gait* and *dancing patella* involve dynamic or functional associations that may be less easily encoded than static, visually descriptive metaphors. The moderate recognition rates imply partial cognitive accessibility—students may recognize the metaphor but lack the precise pathophysiological association needed to answer correctly.

Low performance (<40% correct)

Lowest accuracy was seen in **Q3 (Minerva cast, 29%)** and **Q6 (frog-leg position, 35%)**. These terms, though occasionally metaphorical, rely more heavily on historical or procedural knowledge than on intuitive visual analogies. *Minerva cast* refers to a specific orthopaedic immobilization device named after the Roman goddess of wisdom, rather than a descriptive image of form or movement. Similarly, *froggy position*, though visually descriptive, may be less frequently encountered or emphasized in contemporary training. The low performance in these items likely reflects both reduced curricular exposure and less immediately resonant metaphorical imagery.

Overall, the data illustrate that metaphoric vividness and clinical salience play a central role in medical term retention and recognition. Terms that evoke clear visual or kinaesthetic imagery—especially those grounded in natural forms or animal analogies—tend to elicit higher accuracy. Conversely, abstract, historical,

or procedural terms are more vulnerable to recall failure. This finding aligns with broader cognitive-linguistic evidence that metaphor enhances conceptual mapping and mnemonic accessibility by linking unfamiliar medical phenomena to familiar perceptual experiences.

From a pedagogical standpoint, these results emphasise the importance of integrating metaphoric reasoning and visual learning into medical education. The use of visual aids, case-based imagery, and explicit discussion of the linguistic origins of eponyms may strengthen retention and conceptual understanding. Furthermore, awareness of the metaphorical underpinnings of medical terminology can deepen students' appreciation of the interplay between language, perception, and diagnostic cognition.

Metaphor in medical terminology functions as both a linguistic and cognitive bridge between scientific abstraction and lived experience. Particularly within orthopaedics and traumatology, metaphorical terms embody the human tendency to make the invisible visible, to translate anatomy and pathology into comprehensible and memorable forms. The study conducted at the Medical University of Plovdiv demonstrates that while metaphor enhances comprehension and memory, its pedagogical effectiveness depends on context, clarity, and appropriate use.

Ultimately, metaphor is not merely a rhetorical embellishment but a conceptual tool integral to the construction, dissemination, and internalization of medical knowledge. Recognizing its dual role—as a source of insight and potential misunderstanding—invites educators and practitioners alike to employ metaphor consciously and critically in the training of future medical professionals.

References

1. Aristotle. *Poetics*. Heath M, translator. London: Penguin Classics; 1996.
2. Brazhuk Y. The sources of metaphorization and peculiarities of the metaphorization process in medical terminology. *Sci Educ New Dimens Philol*. 2017;118.
3. Cook DA, Levinson AJ, Garside S, Dupras DM, Erwin PJ, Montori VM. Instructional design variations in internet-based learning for health professions education: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Acad Med*. 2008;83(5):495–503.
4. Epstein RM. Assessment in medical education. *N Engl J Med*. 2007;356(4):387–96.
5. Faber, Pamela (ed.). 2012. *A Cognitive Linguistics View of Terminology and Specialized Language*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
6. Frank JR, Snell L, ten Cate O, et al. Competency-based medical education: theory to practice. *Med Teach*. 2010;32(8):638–45.
7. Gupta N, Varma M, Kumar TP. Parrot's beak sign in brucellosis. *QJM*. 2025. doi:10.1093/qjmed/haef106
8. Kuhn TS. Metaphor in science. In: Ortony A, editor. *Metaphor and Thought*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1993.
9. Lakoff G, Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press; 1980.
10. Masukume G, Zumla A. Analogies and metaphors in clinical medicine. *Clin Med (Lond)*. 2012;12(1):55–6. doi:10.7861/clinmedicine.12-1-55
11. MedlinePlus [Internet]. Walking abnormalities. [reviewed 2023 Jan 23; cited 2025 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://medlineplus.gov/ency/article/003199.htm>
12. Mirchev, D., Oprova, Y. (2023). Errors in the use of medical terminology in Latin in the regulatory framework of the Republic of Bulgaria. In Tenth International Scientific Conference "Language, Science, Communications and Sport – 60 Years of Academic Education": Collection of Papers (Volume 2, ISBN 978-619-221-452-4) Varna: Publishing House of the Medical University – Varna.
13. Mirchev, D., Oprova, Y. (2024). The eternal significance of the Latin language for science. Contemporary challenges in teaching Latin with medical terminology and regulatory framework. In First National Scientific Conference with International Participation "Language and Science": Collection of Papers (ISBN 978-619-237-129-6). Plovdiv: Publishing House of the Medical University – Plovdiv.
14. Nicol DJ, Macfarlane-Dick D. Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: a model and seven principles of good feedback practice. *Stud High Educ*. 2006;31(2):199–218.
15. Oprova, Ya., Mirchev, D. Terms for medicine and treatment in Latin and Greek terminology, Collection of articles, Plovdiv, 2018, ISSN: 978-619-237-013-8. Oprova, Ja., Mirchev, D. Termini za lekarstvo i lechenie v latinskata i gr"ckata terminologija, Sbornik statii, Plovdiv, 2018, ISSN: 978-619-237-013-8.
16. Ortony A, editor. *Metaphor and Thought*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1979.
17. Paivio A. Dual coding theory and education. In: Kozma RB, editor. *Learning with Media*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates; 1991.
18. Skelton JR, Wearn AM, Hobbs FR. A concordance-based study of metaphoric expressions used by general practitioners and patients in consultation. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2002;52(475):114–8.
19. Smith T, Crocker J, Dodd K, Richards SH. Teaching pediatric orthopaedics: is it adequately covered in undergraduate medical curricula? *J Child Orthop*. 2014;8(2):123–9.
20. Stanford Medicine 25. The knee exam. Stanford University School of Medicine. Available from: <https://med.stanford.edu/content/sm/stanfordmedicine25/the25/knee.html>
21. Stanley D, McCarthy S. Clinical tests for knee effusion: a systematic review. *Physiotherapy*. 2003;89(3):162–9.
22. Stavrev P, Atanasov A. Orthopedics and Traumatology. Plovdiv; 2004. Stavrev P, Atanasov A. OrtopediJa i Travmatologija. Plovdiv; 2004.
23. Stavrev V. *Orthopedics for Medical Students*. Plovdiv; 2012.
24. Stavrev V. *Traumatology for Medical Students*. Plovdiv; 2012.
25. Usyk G, Kyrylenko T. Метафора як спосіб утворення медичної термінології [Metaphor as a way of terms coinage in medicine]. *Adv Linguist*.

2020;(5):62–7.
5339.2020.5.203922

doi:10.20535/2617-

26. Yefimova OS. Metaphorization as a source of emergence of some medical terms. *Russ Linguist Bull.* 2024;2(50).